

PARTICLE PLACEMENT IN AN ATOM BASED ON THE FERM-DIRAC AND BOSE-EINSTEIN DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO THE VALUE OF THE SPIN QUANTUM NUMBER

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Abstract. *The article discusses the significance of the arrangement of atoms and molecules in a substance that forms stable systems, such as an atom and a molecule. It examines the patterns of combining elementary particles, such as electrons and nuclei, which are present in nature, to form atoms, as well as their distribution within an atom. The article provides information about the differences in elementary particles, which have been verified by scientists, based on their spin values, and how they follow different distributions based on their spin values, as well as their arrangement within an atom based on the Pauli principle. The Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein distributions are the fundamental concepts of atomic and molecular physics and provide a complete answer to the question of whether the system and the physical properties of a molecule or an atom depend on the arrangement of the elementary particles that make up the system.*

Keywords: *elementary particles, distribution law, Fermi-Dirac distribution, Bose-Einstein distribution, spin, Pauli principle, fermion, boson.*

Introduction

In nature, atoms and molecules occur both as individual systems and, through mutual combination, form higher-level systems—substances. As we know, substances occur in nature in four aggregate states. So what exactly distinguishes these states from one another? Even substances with identical composition are not uncommon in nature when they differ in their physical properties and characteristics. Therefore, the main reason for the variation in the properties of matter must be some factor other than its structural composition. In classical physics, the molecules and atoms in matter are regarded as stable systems composed of associations of elementary particles. However, after 1900, as knowledge of quantum physics took shape, it became clear that the small systems forming the basis of matter actually obey the laws of quantum physics. For example, based on Niels Bohr's postulates on atomic structure, it was proven that the atomic system is a complex quantum system. The nucleus and electron within the system are themselves quantum systems, and there are specific laws governing their behavior as a whole. These laws, following the discovery of electron and nuclear spin, established the conditions for the stability of the atomic system.

We classify the numerous elementary particles found in nature according to their charge, rest mass, lifetime, and spin quantum number. Essentially, elementary particles are divided into those with integer spin quantum numbers and those with half-integer spin quantum numbers. We group particles with an integer spin quantum number as bosons and those with a half-integer spin quantum number as fermions. Fermions include quarks (adron, baryon, nucleon, atom, molecule) and lepton particles, while bosons include photon, gluon, and graviton particles.

Atoms and molecules that participate in the formation of matter are composed precisely of these elementary particles. Therefore, once the existence of the electron within the atom was proven, all atoms in nature were considered to have been formed as a result of electron-nucleus interactions, these atoms should differ from one another in the number of electrons and in the arrangement of electrons in their orbitals and in their energy states, and an answer to this question was not found quickly. In 1922, according to the atomic model proposed by Niels Bohr, electrons confined to a single orbit occupy stable “closed shells” corresponding to the numbers 2, 8, 18, Pauli attempted to explain these empirically determined numbers. In a 1924 scientific paper published by Stoner, it was suggested that the numbers proposed by Bohr could be the value of the principal quantum number; Pauli, on the basis of this scientific idea, attempted to explain these empirically determined numbers.

Analysis of relevant literature (Literature review).

Macroscopic systems consist of a very large number of molecules and atoms. The molecules in these systems are arranged according to certain laws. The motion of molecules and atoms can be explained by the laws of classical or quantum mechanics. For example, L. D. Landau and E. M. Lifshitz. In the book “Course of Theoretical Physics, Vol. 5: Statistical Physics, Part 1” [1], it is stated that “According to statistical laws, because bodies consist of a large number of particles, their motion cannot be fully explained by the laws of classical mechanics.” The distribution laws for particles differ, and depending on which wave function is used to describe their motion—namely whether they have symmetric or antisymmetric wave functions—their spin value is distinguished as integer or half-integer. If the particle spin has half-integer quantum numbers, then the Pauli principle applies, and there can be no more than one particle in each quantum state; the distribution is described by the Fermi–Dirac distribution. Conversely, if the particle spin has integer quantum numbers, it is described by a symmetric wave function, and any number of particles can occupy each quantum state. This particle distribution is called the Bose–Einstein distribution. According to the Bose–Einstein distribution, the number of particles in gases

is calculated using the formula
$$N = \frac{gVm^3}{2^{1/2}} \frac{16\pi}{h^3} \int_0^\infty \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon d \epsilon}}{e^{(\epsilon-\mu)/T} \pm 1} .$$
 The author suggested that particles

distribute differently in solids or gases depending on the value of their spin quantum number, and that in statistical analysis the appropriate distribution for a given particle should be determined precisely by that quantum number value.

When we analyze A.I. Morozov's “Electronic Fermi Liquid in Metals, 2016” [2], the author examines the filling of electronic states at absolute zero temperature, Since fermions obey the Pauli principle, in the given case, according to the complete set of quantum numbers, there should not be more than one electron. As we know, at absolute zero temperature the system is in its lowest energy state; we fill the states in order of electron energy, which increases monotonically. All quantum states have wave vectors in the state, The electrons' Fermi wave vector corresponds to the Fermi momentum. The threshold energy between $|k| \leq k_F$ occupied and unoccupied states is called the $k_F = (3\pi^2 n_e)^{1/3} \approx 10^{10} m^{-1}$

Fermi energy - $E_F = \frac{h^2 k_F^2}{8\pi^2 m} = \frac{p_F^2}{2m}$. Accordingly, from the equality, the electron's Fermi momentum is $p_F = \frac{h}{2\pi} k_F = 10^{-24} kg \cdot m / s$.

Research Methodology

To ensure our students fully grasp the topic, we must first explain the structural composition of complex systems like molecules and atoms, as well as quantum states, quantum numbers, and the Pauli principle, and then explain the laws of distribution. In molecular physics, the Maxwell distribution of molecular velocities and the Boltzmann distribution of pressures are studied. If a student has mastered these topics well, they will know that elementary particles, such as electrons in the atoms that make up molecules, can change their speed during their motion. That is, based on which energy level the electron occupies in the atomic system, its momentum and velocity can be calculated.

Initially, to explain the topic, we will use the comparative method to study the general and specific parameters of the Bose-Einstein, Fermi-Dirac, and Boltzmann distributions.

Boltzmann distribution	Fermi-Dirac distribution	Bose-Einstein distribution
$\langle n \rangle = \frac{1}{\exp(\frac{\varepsilon - \mu}{k_B T})}$	$\langle n \rangle = \frac{1}{\exp(\frac{\varepsilon - \mu}{k_B T}) - 1}$	$\langle n \rangle = \frac{1}{\exp(\frac{\varepsilon - \mu}{k_B T}) + 1}$
The particles are the same	The particles are the same	The particles are the same
$Z = (Z_1)^N / N!$ $n \ll 1$	The spin quantum number is an integer: (0,1,2,...)	The spin quantum number is a half-integer: (1/2, 3/2, 5/2...)
Spin is irrelevant	Bozons	Fermions
Particles are localized (not represented by a ψ function)	The ψ function representing the state of the particles is completely symmetric.	The ψ function representing the state of the particles is fully antisymmetric.
Gas molecules at the lowest density	Photons, atoms, ${}^4\text{He}$	Electron, proton, neutron
The number of particles in the microenvironment is unlimited.	The number of particles in the microenvironment is unlimited.	In a single quantum state, there cannot be more than one particle with the same quantum numbers.

Figure 1. Graph of the Bose-Einstein and Fermi-Dirac distributions for the same parameter.

Based on the distribution of particles by velocity and pressure, we determine that, according to their quantum number values, they obey Fermi–Dirac and Bose–Einstein distributions. Since the elementary particles in the atomic system—electrons, protons, and neutrons—are fermions, they obey the Fermi-Dirac distribution. Looking at the Fermi-Dirac distribution graph, no sharp spikes are observed in the graph of the number of particles versus particle energy, in accordance with the Pauli principle. The curve changes gradually as the temperature decreases. Also, if we compare it with the Bose-Einstein distribution graph for bosons, such as the photon, we see that the photon's energy can be zero, which is evident in the graph. For fermions, however, the energy cannot be zero. Bose-Einstein statistics describe how bosons are more likely to be found in the lowest energy state.

In quantum mechanics, unlike classical mechanics, a particle moving in a specific quantum state undergoes finite motion. Each quantum state has multiple energy levels distinguished by the spin quantum number. In finite motion, each energy level takes on discrete values. The electron gas obeys the Fermi–Dirac distribution; according to the Pauli principle, free electrons interact with each other, and this interaction is not forceful but quantum in nature. That is, a free electron is not absolutely free. The Fermi-Dirac distribution of electrons in the electron gas is:

$$f(E, T) = \left\{ 1 + \exp \frac{E - E_p}{kT} \right\}^{-1}$$

E_p - The value of the Fermi-Dirac function is always equal to $\frac{1}{2}$. This function determines the maximum number of electrons with energy E that can exist in a single quantum state. The Bose–Einstein distribution applies to an ideal gas of free bosons. The bosons do not interact with external fields or with each other. The particle's state, in terms of its momentum and spin projection, takes only two values according to the $g = 2s + 1$ Landé factor. The number of states p and $p + dp$ in the range of momentum values and is calculated using the

$$dN_p = \frac{gV4\pi}{h^3} p^2 dp \text{ formula .}$$

Analysis and results

An atom is a stable system, and its constituent particles are the electron and the proton, Since the neutron is a fermion, knowing the distribution of electrons across an atom's energy levels is extremely important, because atomic systems—by virtue of having the same electrons arranged in different energy states in varying numbers and energy levels—produce different atoms. Therefore, students are observed to master the Fermi-Dirac distribution well based on their strong understanding of the unique and common properties of boson and fermion particles. The Fermi-Dirac distribution, in turn, provides the basis for accurately calculating the energy levels of electrons, protons, and neutrons in an atom. In Dirac's formula for calculating the energy of the relativistic electron, the sum of the electron's momentum and its intrinsic magnetic moment is included in the total momentum. This quantity, in turn, differs for each of the electron's energy levels. In the Fermi-Dirac distribution, the level energy of electrons depends on the magnitude of the Fermi wave vector. The value of the Fermi wave vector, in turn, is determined by the energy level of the orbit in which the electron is moving.

Students understand that the main difference between the Fermi–Dirac distribution and the Bose–Einstein distribution is that the former is valid only for fermions—which, by Pauli's principle, can occupy atomic energy levels with a half-integer spin quantum number—and that

they can move within those levels. As a result, when filling atoms with electrons according to the Mendeleev system of chemical elements, they place exactly one electron in each state with exactly the same set of quantum numbers, based on the values of the spin quantum number's projections onto the spatial axes. As a result of understanding how electrons are arranged in an atom, they come to understand why the first period elements are filled with hydrogen and helium.

In molecular physics, the Maxwell, Bose-Einstein, and Fermi-Dirac distributions study the arrangement of molecules within materials. Considering that the atoms from which molecules are composed also obey these same laws, The Fermi-Dirac distribution is considered the primary distribution explaining the arrangement of electrons in an atom. This is because electrons in atoms simultaneously undergo very complex motions. As a result, atoms with the exact same number of electrons are observed to have two different energies at the same time. The primary reason for this is the change in the value of the resulting spin due to the orientation of the electrons. For example, the helium atom, which has only two electrons, when transitioning to excited levels, can exist in two orthogonal spin states: the parahelium state with spin zero and the orthhelium state with spin one. According to the Dirac equation, the total energy yields two different values. As a result, in the multiplet state, fine structure singlet and triplet splittings occur.

Conclusion/Recommendations

In conclusion, it can be said that electrons in atoms are arranged according to a specific pattern. We studied how the spin—the intrinsic moment that arises from electrons' rotation around their own axis in addition to their orbital motion around the nucleus—causes their orientation to change in energy levels. Since the spin magnetic quantum number can only take on two values, electrons in a single energy level can only have two orientations. As a result, students can write the electron formula and configuration of an element's atom by filling its energy levels with electrons in antiparallel arrangement. For this, they must have a good grasp of the differences between the distributions and their importance in distinguishing particle locations.

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